

Treatment of Raw Domestic Wastewater Using Spent Tea, Sawdust, and Charcoal as an Adsorbent

Zindagi Malhotra
American Embassy School, New Delhi

ABSTRACT

Domestic wastewater is an ever-growing problem that poses significant environmental challenges. This wastewater in homes and buildings often contains pollutants, heavy metals, and dangerous pathogens. Traditional wastewater treatment plants are capital-intensive and extremely costly facilities. They need to be more sustainable and attainable to use on a small scale. Past research has analyzed the effectiveness of other adsorbents on different kinds of wastewater and has successfully mitigated some unwanted chemicals. In this paper, easily accessible adsorbents such as spent tea leaves, sawdust, and charcoal were tested for their efficiency in treating domestic wastewater. Recycled plastic bottles were used to create a filtering mechanism that allowed wastewater to be poured over the adsorbent, filtering through and then dripping into another glass through a hole in the bottle cap. The effectiveness was tested by measuring the physicochemical parameters of the wastewater pre and post-passing through the adsorption filter. The charcoal removed 95% of turbidity from the wastewater. Charcoal, Sawdust, and the combined filter significantly lowered the pH of the raw wastewater from 9.5 to 7.0-7.5, however Spent tea filter drastically lowered the pH to 5.5. All the filters showed a reduction in the levels of fluoride, nitrate, iron, hardness, and chloride. This study suggests that these adsorbents have the potential to be used to treat wastewater containing organic pollutants sustainably and conveniently, while charcoal proved to be the most effective. Hence, in the future charcoal can be utilized in the treatment of domestic wastewater.

Keywords: wastewater, adsorbent, charcoal, sawdust, spent tea, physicochemical analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Domestic wastewater is an ever-growing problem that poses significant environmental challenges. This wastewater in homes and buildings often contains pollutants, heavy metals, and dangerous pathogens (Osman et al., 2016). In urban areas globally, approximately 380 billion cubic meters of water is generated annually (WWAP, 2017). Only about 56% of this water is properly treated, leaving a significant amount untreated in the environment

(Corcoran et al., 2010). This water can have severe consequences on the population and society. Public health, water bodies nearby, soil quality, and more are all negatively affected if this water is not treated properly.

Some available strategies are being utilized to tackle this problem. Traditional Wastewater Treatment Plants (WWTPs) are the conventional strategy, involving capital-intensive facilities. The process includes primary sedimentation, biological treatment, and chemical coagulation. The cost for this method of treatment can range from three to five crore rupees per MLD of treatment capacity, in addition to a periodic maintenance expense (CPCB, 2013). Another popular strategy is known as decentralized treatment systems, which occur at a smaller scale and often utilize natural treatment methods such as constructed wetlands. The cost for these treatments typically ranges from one to two crore rupees per MLD. However, they have some requirements for large areas of land which makes them less practical in urban areas (Vymazal, 2011).

Another strategy is the use of naturally adsorbent materials - such as spent tea, sawdust, and charcoal, which are low-cost and sustainable - to remove contaminants from wastewater. Due to their characteristics such as high surface area, porosity, and having functional groups that can bind to pollutants, organic materials such as spent tea leaves, sawdust, and charcoal have demonstrated potential as adsorbents in wastewater treatment (Das & Kumar, 2021). First, spent tea leaves are an extremely common waste product of households, particularly in India, one of the world's largest tea producers and consumers. Polyphenols and other organic chemicals found in these leaves interact with and absorb organic contaminants and heavy metals, proving useful in the treatment of wastewater (Zia et al., 2020). Similarly, the porosity of sawdust allows for effective adsorbent of unwanted heavy metals and contaminants in water. According to a study conducted by Daski et al. (2022), it was found that spent tea leaves were successful in removing high percentages of organic pollutants from wastewater. In another study by Yadav Anu (2015), charcoal and other inexpensive sorbents aided in the removal of organic matter and ions in wastewater.

Particularly for a country as densely populated as India, more suitable methods of cleaning domestic wastewater should be explored; considering the cost, space, and environmental footprint of the systems. The standard larger processes do not utilize natural adsorbents so that they could be recreated at a smaller scale - in homes, for example. Taking this into consideration, it is imperative to research natural adsorbents such as spent tea, sawdust, and charcoal further and explore their use for the treatment of domestic wastewater. This study aims to address this gap by evaluating the efficiency of spent tea, sawdust, and charcoal, and

a combination of all three in removing contaminants from domestic wastewater through different tests of the physicochemical properties of the water.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.1 Materials:

2.1.1 Spent Tea Leaves:

Spent tea leaves exhibit good adsorption properties due to the presence of polyphenols, which can bind with heavy metals and organic pollutants. The porous structure and surface functional groups in tea leaves make them effective at adsorbing contaminants such as dyes, oils, and certain metal ions from water.

Spent tea leaves (300 g wet powder) were collected from home use over one week. After each use, the leaves were removed from the pot, dried with paper towels, and stored in the refrigerator to prevent mold growth. At the end of the collection period, the tea leaves were spread on a baking tray and sun-dried for two hours to reduce moisture content. The dried leaves were then ground into a fine powder using a grinder and stored in an airtight container.

2.1.2 Sawdust:

Sawdust, composed primarily of cellulose, lignin, and hemicellulose, has a high surface area and porous structure, enabling it to adsorb organic compounds, oils, and heavy metals. Its efficiency can be enhanced when chemically treated, although even in raw form, it shows moderate adsorption capacity. Sawdust (200 g powder) was purchased commercially from Amazon.

2.1.3 Activated Charcoal:

Activated charcoal is a highly porous material with an extensive surface area, making it one of the most effective adsorbents. It can adsorb a wide range of contaminants, including organic pollutants, chemicals, and heavy metals, by trapping them within its pores through physical and chemical interactions. Activated charcoal (200 g powder) was purchased commercially from Amazon for use in the filtration experiments.

2.1.4 Tara Life Water Testing Kit:

The Tara Life kit is an 8-parameter water testing kit used for physicochemical analysis of water samples. It measures physical parameters such as pH, turbidity, and

hardness alongside chemical parameters such as chloride, fluoride, iron, and nitrate. The kit provides sufficient materials to conduct 100 tests for each parameter.

Fig1: Tara Life water testing kit

2.2 Sample preparation:

The domestic wastewater used in this study was collected from my home and included a combination of sink, shower, and washing machine effluent. The study required approximately 3-4 liters of wastewater.

2.3 Procedure for preparing the filter assembly:

1. To begin, cut off the bottom of a 500 ml plastic bottle.
2. Next, unscrew the bottle's lid, make a small hole in the center using a pin, and put some cotton wool inside the lid.
3. Then screw the lid back on and turn the bottle upside down.
4. Add around 200 of the adsorbing material under study into the bottle, then pour around 500 ml of the wastewater from the top.
5. The water passes through the cotton filter and drips into a beaker.
6. Once filtered, test the physicochemical parameters of both the raw and filtered water to evaluate the process's efficiency.
7. Finally, repeat steps 1-6 for the combined filter utilizing a 1:1:1 concentration of all three materials under study and assess their combined efficiency.

Fig 2: The Sawdust filter setup

2.4 Physico-chemical Analysis:

The physicochemical analysis of wastewater is essential for assessing the quality of both treated and raw water. The physical parameters, such as pH, turbidity, and hardness, provide insights into the water's acidity/alkaline nature, suspended matter, and calcium and Magnesium content. Additionally, chemical parameters such as chloride, fluoride, iron, and nitrate were analyzed to identify the presence of contaminants and assess the water's usability for allied usage.

1. pH

1. Take a piece of pH paper
2. Dip pH paper into the water sample
3. Let it dry for a few seconds
4. Compare the colour with the pH colour chart

Fig 3: pH colour chart

2. Turbidity

1. Place a piece of plain white paper on the floor
2. Hold the turbidity tube about 8 cm off the ground

3. Look through the open, upper end of the tube to ensure the black cross at the bottom of the tube is visible
4. Slowly pour the water sample into the tube, while observing the black cross
5. Stop pouring the sample when the cross is no longer visible
6. Measure turbidity value based on marks on the tube

3. Hardness

1. Take 5mL of water sample
2. Add 1-2 drops of Ammonia Buffer to raise the pH to 10
3. Add a pinch of Eriochrome black T-powder
4. Take 1 ml of EDTA solution in 1ml syringe without any air bubbles
5. Titrate until the colour changes from wine red to blue

Calculation:

$$\text{mL of EDTA used in titration} * 400 = \text{hardness (mg/L)}$$

4. Chloride

1. Take 5mL of water sample
2. Check the pH of the solution - should be between 7 and 10
3. Add 1 drop of Potassium Chromate
4. Take 1 mL of Silver Nitrate solution
5. Titrate till the colour changes to a permanent brick red

Calculation:

$$\text{mL of Silver Nitrate used in titration} * 354.5 = \text{chlorides (mg/L)}$$

5. Fluoride

1. Take 50mL of water sample
2. Add 2.5 mL of Zirconyl Alizarine
3. Mix the solution by pouring it into another test tube
4. Allow the solution to develop colour for one hour
5. Compare the colour with the Fluoride Colour Comparison Chart
6. Record the matching colour corresponding values

Fig 4: Fluoride colour chart

6. Iron

Procedure:

1. Take 20 mL of water sample

2. Add ½ spoon of Reagent Fe - A, then shake solution to dissolve
3. Add ½ spoon of Reagent Fe - B using another spoon, then shake
4. After five minutes, compare the colour with the Iron Colour Comparison Chart
5. Record the matching colour corresponding values

Fig 3: Iron colour chart

7. Nitrate

1. Take 5 mL of water sample
2. Add 1 spoon of Reagent NO₃ - A, then shake the solution to dissolve
3. Add ½ spoon of Reagent NO₃ - B using another spoon, then shake
4. After ten minutes, compare the colour with the Iron Colour Comparison Chart
5. Record the matching colour corresponding values

Fig 3: Nitrate colour chart

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

3.1 Raw Wastewater Sample:

Sr. No.	Parameter	Observed value	Acceptable range
1	pH	9.5	6.5-8.5
2	Turbidity (NTU)	145	5-10
3	Fluoride (mg/L)	3.0	0.8-1.0
4	Nitrate (mg/L)	90	45
5	Iron (mg/L)	2.6	0.3-1.0
6	Hardness (mg/L)	800	300-600
7	Chloride (mg/L)	1200	250-1000

Table 1: Physicochemical Properties of Raw Domestic Wastewater

3.2 Treated wastewater sample:

Sr. No.	Parameter	Spent Tea	Saw dust	Charcoal	Combined filter	Acceptable range
1	pH	5.5	7	7.5	7.2	6.5-8.4
2	Turbidity (NTU)	50 NTU	22 NTU	8NTU	19 NTU	5-10
3	Fluoride (mg/L)	0.7	0.8	1.2	1.8	1-1.5
4	Nitrate (mg/L)	30	55	40	35	45
5	Iron (mg/L)	2.0	1.5	0.25	0.7	0.3-1.0
6	Hardness (mg/L)	690	450	580	500	300-600
7	Chloride (mg/L)	1250	230.425	709	650	250-1000

Table 2: Physicochemical Properties of Treated Wastewater

pH:

The pH of raw wastewater was first measured at 9.5, suggesting alkaline conditions. Activated charcoal, sawdust, and the combination filter successfully reduced the pH to the neutral range of 7.0-7.5, indicating their potential for pH stabilization in wastewater treatment. This neutralization is especially crucial for achieving environmental discharge criteria and making the water safe to reuse. However, the spent tea leaf filter drastically dropped the pH to 5.5, making the water acidic. While discarded tea leaves have strong adsorption characteristics for other pollutants, the significant pH reduction indicated that they may not be suitable for applications that need neutral pH values.

Fig 3: pH variation in pre and post-treatment of domestic wastewater

Turbidity:

From Table 1. it can be seen that the Turbidity of the raw domestic wastewater was 145 NTU. After passing the sample through the individual filters, it can be observed that the Turbidity of the domestic waste has reduced significantly. Table 2 shows that the Charcoal filter has substantially reduced the wastewater Turbidity from 145 NTU to 8NTU (95% reduction efficiency). This can be due to the high surface area and porous structure of activated charcoal, which allows it to adsorb a significant amount of suspended particles. The sawdust and spent tea leaves also contribute to turbidity reduction to 22NTU and 50 NTU, which is less efficient than charcoal, reflecting their lower adsorption capacity for fine particulates. The combination filter comprising charcoal, sawdust, and wasted tea leaves demonstrated significant turbidity removal (19 NTU). The filters' efficiency can be summarized as follows: charcoal > combined filter > sawdust > spent tea. The findings indicate activated charcoal as a superior adsorbent for removing suspended particles from wastewater as it has reduced the turbidity of raw wastewater usage within the permissible range of 5-10 NTU.

Fig 4: Turbidity variation in pre and post-treatment of domestic wastewater

Fluoride:

Fluoride ions serve a dual purpose in water supply. A high concentration of F- causes dental fluorosis (tooth disfigurement). At the same time, a concentration below 0.8 mg/L causes 'dental caries'. As a result, it is critical to keep F - concentrations in drinking water between 0.8-1 mg/L. Table 1 shows the fluoride content of the raw domestic wastewater was 3.0mg/L & Table 2. shows the concentration of fluoride in filtered samples as 0.7mg/L, 0.8mg/L, 1.2mg/L & 1.8 mg/L for Spent tea, Saw dust, Activated Charcoal powder, and Combined filter respectively. These results suggest that a Saw dust filter is the most suitable adsorbent for fluoride removal, while the other materials can provide supplementary support.

Fig 5: Variation in Fluoride content of pre and post-treatment domestic wastewater

Nitrate:

The nitrate limit in potable water is 45 mg/L. Table 1 shows that the raw wastewater had a nitrate concentration of 90 mg/L. The nitrate concentration decreased drastically when the wastewater was treated using the four different filter materials. All adsorbents removed nitrate, with spent tea leaves being the most effective, lowering the nitrate content from 90 mg/L to 30 mg/L. Nitrate removal is critical for preventing eutrophication and maintaining water quality. The combined filter also functioned well, demonstrating that a combination of different adsorbents can improve nitrate removal. Sawdust had moderate efficacy in lowering nitrate levels, however the concentration in the treated water remained higher than the permitted level.

Fig 6: Variation in Nitrate concentration of pre and post-treatment domestic wastewater

Iron:

The acceptable range for iron in water is 0.3-1.0 ppm. Table 1 shows that the concentration of iron in raw wastewater is 2.6 mg/L, which is higher than the range. Table 2 shows that activated charcoal and combination filters considerably reduced iron content in wastewater. Because of its propensity to trap metallic ions in its porous structure, activated charcoal is an excellent adsorber of iron. The combined filter of charcoal, sawdust, and spent tea leaves also effectively reduced iron levels. Spent tea leaves and sawdust had reduced iron removal capacities, most likely due to their smaller surface area and lower metal affinity. These findings support the effectiveness of activated charcoal as a primary adsorbent for metal ion removal in wastewater treatment.

Fig 7: Variation in Iron content of pre and post-treatment domestic wastewater

Hardness:

The recommended range for hardness in water is 300-600 mg/l. Table 1 demonstrates that the concentration of iron in raw wastewater is 800 mg/L, which exceeds the allowable range. Water becomes hard mainly due to an increase in the content of dissolved calcium and magnesium ions. Table 2 demonstrates that sawdust, combination filter, and activated charcoal significantly reduced the hardness of the effluent and brought it within acceptable limits. However, the spent tea filter did not effectively reduce the hardness of the water below the acceptable range. These results show that, while all adsorbents can reduce hardness to some extent, activated charcoal represents the most viable option for this characteristic. The filter's effectiveness in lowering hardness can be summarized as follows: sawdust>combined filter >charcoal >spent tea leaves.

Fig 8: Variation in Hardness of pre and post-treatment domestic wastewater

Chloride:

The acceptable range for chloride content in water ranges from 250-1000 mg/L. Table 1 shows that the chloride level in the raw wastewater was above the acceptable range Viz. 1200 mg/L. Chloride is a challenging ion to remove from wastewater due to its high solubility and stability in water. Table 2 shows that the Chloride level in the wastewater was reduced across all adsorbents, except the spent tea filter, whereas the Saw dust showed the highest removal efficiency. The combined filter also performed well, indicating that the synergy of multiple adsorbents can improve chloride removal. Spent tea leaves increased the chloride content of the wastewater sample, probably due to tea leaves' natural composition or release of chemical components due to interaction with the chemical elements in the wastewater.

Fig 9: Variation in Chloride concentration of pre and post-treatment domestic wastewater

4. CONCLUSION:

The current study highlights the potential of low-cost, accessible adsorbents such as spent tea leaves, sawdust, and activated charcoal for effective domestic wastewater treatment. Among these, activated charcoal proved the most efficient, particularly in turbidity removal and pH stabilization, making it a promising option for decentralized wastewater systems. While all adsorbents contributed to significant contaminant reduction, the combination of materials offers a sustainable, cost-effective alternative to conventional methods, which are often expensive and unsuitable for small-scale applications.

Despite these promising results, the study faced limitations, including the small range of adsorbents tested and challenges with adsorbent availability. Further research is required to explore other materials, optimize their use in different combinations, and assess their long-term performance. Additionally, conducting a cost-benefit analysis would help determine the feasibility of scaling these eco-friendly solutions. Expanding the scope to different industries could further unlock the potential of these natural adsorbents, advancing sustainable wastewater management.

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